

macropterous females were used in all experiments, with 3 replications.

Antifeedant effect of sublethal levels of carbofuran on WBPH was measured as an antifeeding response:

$$\text{Antifeeding response (\%)} = \frac{B-A}{B} 100$$

where A = quantity of honeydew excreted by carbofuran-treated WBPH adults and B = quantity of honeydew excreted by untreated WBPH adults.

As honeydew is produced by a WBPH population, response can be represented as the means of carbofuran concentration causing 50% reduction in feeding (AFC₅₀), calculated by probit regression.

Table 2. Calculated probit regressions and LC₅₀ or AFC₅₀ values for responses of macropterous WBPH females^a treated with carbofuran. Newcastle upon Tyne, United Kingdom.

Treatment	Response	Regression equation ^b	LC ₅₀ or AFC ₅₀	Fiducial limits	Efficiency index ^c
Leaf (µg/cm ²)	Mortality	$y = 2.81 + 3.11x$	0.51	0.44-0.58	4.8
	Antifeed	$y = 4.38 + 0.60x$	0.11	0.05-0.23	
Topical (ng/g)	Mortality	$y = 1.96 + 2.86x$	865.6	656-1126	128.9
	Antifeed	$y = 4.17 + 0.85x$	6.72	4.48-9.70	
Root zone (µM)	Mortality	$y = 2.19 + 2.97x$	8.82	7.45-10.45	9.8
	Antifeed	$y = 3.99 + 1.05x$	0.90	0.64-1.27	

^aMean female body weight = 1.34 mg. y indicates probit, x indicates log (concentration); units are µg/cm² in leaf, ng/g in topical and micromolar (µM) in root-zone treatments. ^cEfficiency index = LC₅₀/AFC₅₀.

Corresponding toxicities (LC₅₀) were determined at 24 h for leaf (indirect) and topical (direct) treatments and at 48 h for root-zone (indirect) application. As contact of insects with carbofuran

increased, antifeeding response at lower concentrations became more evident (shown comparatively at the 50% level by the efficiency index) (Tables 1 and 2). □

Rodent damage in Punjab ricefields, Pakistan

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Preharvest rice crop losses in Pakistan are due primarily to three species of field rats. The lesser bandicoot or Indian mole rat *Bandicota bengalensis* is the most common pest. This species cuts the

Estimated rodent damage and yield reduction in standing rice in major rice-growing areas of Punjab, Pakistan.

District and site	Damage (%/ha)	Area sampled (ha)	Tiller damage (%)	Yield reduction (%)
<i>Sheikhupura</i>				
Ferozwala	2.72	22.06	9.99	7.40
Sheikhupura	2.17	26.11	6.29	3.54
Nankana	5.55	13.17	24.37	22.40
<i>Sialkot</i>				
Pasroor	5.27	25.50	22.40	20.35
Sialkot	2.83	24.90	11.74	9.23
Daska	4.04	25.30	17.04	14.75
<i>Gujranwala</i>				
Hafizabad	3.95	25.30	16.67	14.37
Wazirabad	5.32	24.49	21.72	19.64
Gujranwala	3.63	23.48	14.22	11.81

Rodent damage to standing rice in 3 districts of Punjab, Pakistan.

tillers of the rice crop between nursery and seed hardening stages and also hoards grain. The short-tailed mole rat *Nesokia indica* and the soft-furred rat *Millardia meltada* are also important rodent pests.

We surveyed crop losses to rats in three major rice-growing districts of Punjab: Sheikhupura, Gujranwala, and Sialkot. A multistage sampling technique was used to select subdistricts, villages, and farms; 468 fields on 52 farms were examined and about 100 hills measured for rat injury in each field 2 wk before harvest. Damage was widely distributed (see figure) — 94.1% of the fields surveyed had damaged tillers. In 78.3%, damage averaged 1.7%;

in 15.7%, damage averaged 2.6%. About 52% of the dry fields had rodent burrows inside. The number of burrows on a damage transect line averaged 0.52/field.

Estimated rat damage is summarized in the table. Average cumulative tiller damage was 16.1%, or 3.9%/ha. Damage in Sialkot and Gujranwala districts were similar.

Damage calculated was 15.8% for Basmati and 15.5% for IRRI-6. In Sheikhupura district, IRRI-6 and Basmati did not differ significantly in susceptibility to rat damage ($P > 0.05$). In Sialkot and Gujranwala, the difference between varieties was significant ($P < 0.05$). Varietal susceptibility within

the three districts was significant. There were no significant differences within varieties in the three districts.

Regression analysis developed on simulated rat damage studies indicated that 13.7% yield was lost to rat depredation. □

Composition of the rice leaffolder complex in Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India

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We identified different genera of rice leaffolder or leafroller. Adult moths collected at 2-wk intervals in the wetland ecosystem were sorted based on wing markings. Two genera or species were identified: *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* and *Marasmia patnalis*. *C. medinalis* accounted for 86% of the moths collected (see table). □

Rice leaffolders in Tamil Nadu, India, 1987.

Collection date	Moths collected (no.)	
	<i>C. medinalis</i>	<i>M. patnalis</i>
1 Jan	25	7
15 Jan	41	9
1 Feb	33	9
15 Feb	23	7
1 Mar	33	3
15 Mar	37	6
1 Apr	32	1
15 Apr	34	2
1 May	26	9
15 May	30	3
1 Jun	29	3
15 Jun	33	6
Total	376	65

Abdominal lateral lobe variations in females of *Nilaparvata lugens* biotypes from Korea

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Three biotypes of *N. lugens* isolated in Korea have been maintained for years on differential rice varieties: biotype 1 on variety Chucheongbyeo (no gene for

Camera-lucida drawings of the types of abdominal lobes in female *N. lugens* biotype populations from Korea. Magnification, 78.75X.

Number of brachypterous (BRAC) and macropterous (MAC) females of 3 Korean biotypes of *N. lugens* with different types of abdominal lobes. IRRI, 1987.

Morph	Biotype	Total insects observed	Insects (no.) with given abdominal lobe types ^a					X ²
			I	II	III	IV	v	
BRAC	1	57	23	14	9	10	1	41.70**
	2	77	19	7	5	19	27	
	3	60	30	3	4	15	8	
MAC	1	60	20	0	6	17	17	11.93
	2	50	8	0	3	19	20	
	3	53	12	0	3	10	28	

^aI — normal lobes; II — right and left lobes with discontinuous cut 0.167 mm from posterior tips; III — right lobe with continuous or discontinuous cut, left lobe normal; IV — right lobe normal, left lobe with continuous or discontinuous cut; V — right and left lobes with distinct cuts 0.167 mm from the posterior tips.

resistance), biotype 2 on Cheongcheongbyeo (*Bph 1* gene), and biotype 3 on Milyang 63 (*bph 2* gene). Female brachypters and macropters randomly collected from stock cultures of the 3 biotypes and fixed in 70% alcohol were brought to IRRI, where 50-77 individuals/ biotype were cleared and mounted on glass slides for morphological investigations.

Among *N. lugens* females, five types of abdominal lobes were observed (see figure). The number of brachypterous females of different abdominal lobe types significantly differed among biotypes (see table). Type I lateral lobe

was most frequently found in biotype 3 and biotype 1 and least found in biotype 2. Type V lateral lobe was more common in biotype 2 females than in biotype 3 and biotype 1 females. The number of macropterous females in each category did not significantly differ among biotypes. □

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